

IT VOCABULARY AND POPULAR COMPUTER TERMS IN ENGLISH

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These IT terms in English are generally accepted and can be used by specialists of different professions: from programmers to WEB-developers.

ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of computer technology has given rise to many terms and abbreviations. Most of them are borrowed from the English language. Today, IT terms are used by specialists of all positions and professions, one way or another related to information technology. And in order to keep the conversation going in a narrow circle of professionals, you should familiarize yourself with some popular terminology.

Bug (literally - a bug). A bug is an error in the operation of a program caused by incomplete code. Sometimes a word can take the form of an adjective. Example: "Your code is too buggy".

Cookie (literally cookie). You will often see a pop-up on a website asking you to allow access to cookies. A cookie is a certain amount of data that is stored in the site's database and improves the usability of the site. For example, cookies can contain username and password. Thanks to this, there is no need to enter data every time for authorization on the site. Example: "Please allow this website to use cookies."

DDoS-Attack (abbreviation for Distributed Denial of Service, literally denial of

service). A DDoS attack is a malicious multiple request to servers, the purpose of which is to deny operation. Due to the fact that servers take some time to process a request, they are simply overloaded when the mark of such requests exceeds a critical rate. Example: "The equipment could not withstand a massive DDoS attack, technical work is underway to recover."

VPN (abbreviation for Virtual Private Network). This is a set of technologies and measures that allow you to protect your data, bypass location binding or gain access bypassing locks. Example: "Use a VPN to access this site."

Spam. Spam is the mass mailing of advertising messages to the mail. It is often used by scammers to lure users to third-

party sites. Example: "I received spam in my mail."

Programming terms. Computer terms in English differ depending on the profession and type of activity. Some of them are used to indicate different stages of development, while others can be found in specialized literature. The following dictionary of IT terms in English is very useful for novice programmers and people who want to feel more confident when working with various programs.

Front-end. This term has several meanings: it can be used to indicate an interface (for example, on websites); used to indicate specialization in some professions. Separates front-end and back-end developers. The former are responsible for the appearance of the site, the latter are responsible for its functionality and code. Example: "Looking for a job as HTML Front-end developer".

HTML. The markup language of web pages. He is responsible for positioning text on pages, for correct display on different devices, and much more. Most often used in conjunction with a CSS style sheet, which is responsible for the look and feel of

websites. Example: "The HTML on this site is terrible and has a lot of flaws."

Open Source (literally - open source). The principle of software distribution, which means completely open source for anyone. The author of the software, more often than not, has no monetary benefit when distributed according to this principle. Example: "Linux OS is an Open Source project".

Usability. Evaluation of the ease of use of something (programs, websites). When assessing, features, interface, and navigation are most commonly looked at. Example: "The usability of this site is awful, I couldn't even register."

Backdoor (literally - back door). This term refers to a loophole in the code that allows you to access something. For example, to user databases. Example: "A backdoor was discovered on Facebook, thousands of users' personal data were leaked to the network."

It is possible that you are familiar with the above terminology. However, knowledge of such information will never be superfluous and will greatly simplify the lives of users.

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